

Orbital Coin and Aliens of Malaya: A Blockchain-Powered Ecosystem for Sustainable Transportation and Environmental Conservation in the Philippines

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Abstract:

Orbital Coin (AOM) is a cryptocurrency built on the Polygon network, backed by biodiesel as a commodity, and is accompanied by an NFT membership loyalty card called "Aliens of Malaya." The aim of this project is to create a sustainable ecosystem that benefits both the community and the environment. This whitepaper details the technical aspects, tokenomics, governance, and use cases of AOM and Aliens of Malaya.

Technical Details:

The use of the ERC20 token standard on the Polygon network provides high interoperability with other dApps on the same network, enabling seamless and efficient use of AOM. Additionally, the Polygon network offers significant advantages such as fast transaction speeds and low transaction fees compared to other blockchain networks.

The burn mechanism of AOM tokens is an important feature of tokenomics, reducing the total supply of tokens over time, increasing their scarcity, and potential value. The burning of tokens is achieved by sending them to an address that is provably unspendable, effectively removing them from circulation.

The Aliens of Malaya NFT is minted based on demand via OpenSea and serves as a membership loyalty card for exclusive goods, services, and events. The NFT also contributes towards environmental conservation efforts by planting trees or collecting trash. The Malayan Gazette, a publication by Aliens of Malaya, provides updates on the ecosystem's developments.

Governance:

AOM and Aliens of Malaya are governed through a community-driven approach, with stakeholders having an equal say in the decision-making process. A DAO with 20,000,000 tokens has been created to ensure transparency and accountability in decision-making, providing a mechanism for community members to propose and vote on changes to the ecosystem. Leadership guidance is also provided to ensure smooth operations and avoid conflicts of interest.

Tokenomics:

AOM has a total supply of 500,000,000 tokens, with 327,861,642.704458 tokens burned and 68,685,630.020373 tokens held in a smart contract liquidity pool. The remaining tokens are held by other holders and related smart contracts. The token can be used for purchasing goods and services, trading, and redeeming equivalent units of biodiesel based on the exchange value of AOM and the market value of biodiesel.

Use Cases:

The Aliens of Malaya NFT serves as a membership loyalty card for exclusive goods, services, and events, contributing towards environmental conservation efforts. AOM can be used for purchasing goods and services, trading, and redeeming equivalent units of biodiesel. The project aims to work with traditional jeepney drivers and government agencies to prevent the phase-out of traditional jeepneys by offering biodiesel as a viable alternative.

Roadmap:

The project plans to release the Aliens of Malaya NFT in late 2021 and its early trading on open markets in early 2022. Trees equivalent to the number of Aliens of Malaya purchased will be planted in early 2022. The second version of AOM will be released in mid-2022. In late 2022, OrbitFuel, biodiesel produced by the project, will be market tested. Full market release of OrbitFuel for traditional jeepneys is planned in early 2023, with the project working alongside drivers and government agencies to prevent the phase-out of traditional jeepneys. The project also plans to work with major crypto exchanges in mid-2023 and additional auxiliary projects for Aliens of Malaya. The listing of AOM on Binance or other major exchanges is expected in early 2024, with the project aiming for continued growth in the Kingdom of Malaya digital universe.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, Orbital Coin and Aliens of Malaya represent a novel and innovative approach to creating a sustainable ecosystem that is powered by blockchain technology. The project is aimed at reducing the carbon footprint of traditional jeepneys by using biodiesel, thereby promoting a cleaner and greener environment.

The Orbital Coin cryptocurrency serves as a commodity-backed token that is supported by the underlying commodity of biodiesel. This token is built on the Polygon network, and has a total number of 500,000,000 with a majority of them being burned, thereby increasing the scarcity and value of the token.

Aliens of Malaya, on the other hand, is an NFT that serves as a loyalty card and gives access to exclusive products, services, and events within the ecosystem. It also promotes environmental sustainability by planting trees and collecting trash based on the number of NFTs held.

The governance of the project is community-based with leadership guidance, promoting inclusivity and the involvement of every member in decision-making.

The project roadmap includes the early release of Aliens of Malaya, the planting of trees, the market release of Orbital Coin, and the testing and eventual release of OrbitFuel to be used by traditional jeepney drivers, as well as additional auxiliary projects for Aliens of Malaya.

In summary, the Orbital Coin and Aliens of Malaya project represents a significant step towards promoting environmental sustainability, reducing carbon footprint, and creating a vibrant ecosystem that is powered by blockchain technology. The project has the potential to revolutionize the traditional jeepney industry and promote a cleaner and greener environment in the Philippines and beyond.